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STUDII – ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ – RESEARCHES

Andrei Havinskyi, Małgorzata Rybicka

House of the Funnel Beaker Culture from Vynnyky-*Lisivka*, Western Ukraine

Key words: Funnel Beaker Culture, Tripolye Culture, Volhynian flint.

Cuvinte cheie: cultura Funnel Beaker, cultura Tripolie, silex de Volynia.

Ключевые слова: культура воронковидных сосудов, трипольская культура, волынский кремль.

Andrei Havinskyi, Małgorzata Rybicka

House of the Funnel Beaker Culture from Vynnyky-*Lisivka*, Western Ukraine

The site Vynnyky-*Lisivka* near Lviv is a model example of a settlement of the Funnel Beaker Culture in Western Ukraine. In the following years, the Vynnyky-*Lisivka* site was excavated by numerous researchers. M. Peleschchychyn believed that the complex of Funnel Beaker and Tripolye culture sites in Vynnyky, a part of which is the Vynnyky-*Lisivka* settlement, may prove to be of a particular importance in studies of relations between these two cultural phenomena. Of special interest were clusters of burnt daub unearthed during Peleschchychyn's excavations, which could be interpreted as remains of dwellings. The discovery was made a part of then-ongoing discussion in Polish archaeological literature concerning adaptation of the Tripolye culture tradition of using clay in construction in the Funnel Beaker culture.

The new phase of archaeological research at the Vynnyky-*Lisivka* site started in 2016. That year marks the discovery of a large cluster of burnt daub. The layout of daub fragments in the feature from Vynnyky-*Lisivka* resembles dwellings of the eastern group of the Funnel Beaker culture on the Polish Lowlands.

Andrei Havinskyi, Małgorzata Rybicka

Locuințe specifice culturii Funnel Beaker de la Vynnyky-*Lisivka* din regiunea Ucrainei de Vest

Situl Vynnyky-*Lisivka* de lângă or. Lvov reprezintă un model de așezare cu elemente specifice culturii Funnel Beaker din Ucraina de Vest. În ultimii ani, situl Vynnyky-*Lisivka* a fost investigat sistematic. M. Peleschchychyn consideră că complexul de așezări atribuite culturii Funnel Beaker, de rând cu cele specifice culturii Tripolye din regiunea Vynnyky, unde a și fost descoperită așezarea Vynnyky-*Lisivka*, joacă un rol important în cercetarea relațiilor dintre aceste două fenomene culturale. De un interes aparte au fost concentrațiile de lipitură arsă descoperite în timpul săpăturilor, care pot fi interpretate ca resturi de la locuințe. Aceste afirmații au fost făcute și în coraport cu ideile și discuțiile vehiculate în literatura arheologică poloneză cu privire la adaptarea tradiției tripoliene de a folosi lut în construcția locuințelor specifice culturii Funnel Beaker.

Noua fază a cercetărilor arheologice în situl Vynnyky-*Lisivka* a început în anul 2016. Acel an marchează descoperirea unor concentrații masive de lipitură arsă. Iar, dispunerea fragmentelor de lipitură în situl Vynnyky-*Lisivka* este asemănătoare cu cele descoperite în locuințele din grupul estic al culturii Funnel Beaker.

Андрей Гавинский, Малгожата Рыбicka

Жилища характерные для культуры Воронковидных сосудов из Винники-*Лисивка* на западе Украины

Поселение Винники-*Лисивка* возле г. Львов является образцовым примером поселения культуры воронковидных сосудов в Западной Украине. В последующие годы Винники-*Лисивка* подвергается систематическому исследованию. М. Пелещищын считает, что комплекс поселений культуры воронковидных сосудов и поселений относящиеся к трипольской культуре в Винниках, имеют особое значение для изучения взаимоотношений между этими двумя культурными феноменами. Особый интерес представляли скопления обожженной глины, обнаруженные при раскопках М. Пелещищына, которые можно интерпретировать как остатки от жилищ. Данная интерпретация была сделана в рамках дискуссий, которые велись в то время в польской археологической литературе по поводу адаптации триполитанской традиции использования глины в архитектуре жилищ, характерной для культуры воронковидных стаканов.

Новый этап археологических исследований на поселение Винники-*Лисивка* начался в 2016 году. В том же году была обнаружена большая группа фрагментов обожжённой глины. Расположение фрагментов глины на поселение Винники-*Лисивка* аналогично тем, которые были найдены в жилищах восточной группы культуры воронковидных сосудов.

Introduction

The site Vynnyky-*Lisivka* near Lviv is a model example of a settlement of the the Funnel Beaker Culture (FBC) in Western Ukraine (fig. 1; 2). The discovery of the site in 1959 by B. Woźnicki, outside the well-established Bug River oecumene of the FBC, confirmed earlier suggestions concerning possible wider range of this culture expressed by K. Jażdżewski over 20 years prior [Jażdżewski 1936]¹.

In the following years, the Vynnyky-*Lisivka* site was excavated by numerous researchers, including I.K. Svesnikov [Sveshnikov 1976, 44], M. Peleshchychyn [Peleshchishin 1995, 1-9; 1998, 15; 1999, 104], P. Dovgan, V. Konopla, T. Milan [Dovgan' et al. 2008] and A. Hawinskyj.

Mykola Peleshchychyn believed that the complex of FBC and Tripolye Culture (TC) sites in Vynnyky, a part of which is the Vynnyky-*Lisivka* settlement, may prove to be of a particular importance in studies of relations between these two cultural phenomena. The scholar expressed that “The situation in Vynnyky indicates (the possibility of) [...] forming joint settlements with a mixed population” [Peleshchishin 1998a, 191], inhabited by people of both the FBC and TC. The above-quoted remarks brought new attention of researchers to the Vynnyky area. Of special interest were clusters of burnt daub unearthed during Peleshchychyn’s excavations, which could be interpreted as remains of dwellings [Peleshchishin 1994; 1995; 1998]. The discovery was made a part of then-ongoing discussion in Polish archaeological literature concerning adaptation of the TC tradition of using clay in construction in the FBC *milieu* [Kowalczyk 1958; Koško 1981; 1988; Gumiński 1989; Papiernik, Rybicka 2002].

Dwellings from Vynnyky-*Lisivka*

The new phase of archaeological research at the Vynnyky-*Lisivka* site started in 2016². That year marks the discovery of a large cluster of burnt

1. According to K. Jażdżewski (1936), the eastern borderland of the southern group of the FBC should extend to the northern part of what was then the Lviv province, as well as western and northern part of the Volhynia province. K. Jażdżewski believed that the southern limits of the FBC reached the northern outskirts of the former Stanisławów province.

2. The research was carried out as part of the NCN Opus 8 “Between the East and the West. Dynamic of Social Changes from the Eastern Carpatians to the Dnieper in the 4th – beginning of 3rd Millennium BC” project.

Fig. 1. Vynnyky-*Lisivka*, region Lviv. Location of site at Vynnyky-*Lisivka*.

Fig. 2. Vynnyky-*Lisivka*, region Lviv. A view of settlements Vynnyky-*Zhupan* and Vynnyky-*Lysivka*, near Lviv (photo: A. Hawinskyj).

daub (fig. 3; 4) [Rybicka et al. 2018; Diachenko et al. 2019]. Excavation of the surroundings of the cluster were continued in 2017-2019 (fig. 3-5). These field-

Fig. 3. Vynnyky-Lysivka, region Lviv. Location of daub and post-holes in excavation trench 3 from the year 2016. 1 – daub; 2 – stones; 3 – fossil tree; 4 – postholes.

works resulted in a discovery of remains of structure build using construction clay [Diachenko et al. 2019], and the second identified only from post-holes (fig. 5). In order to determine what was the

function of unearthed clusters of daub and how the space around them was managed, the pottery finds from the archaeological trenches were analysed not only in relation to the entire collection, but also in

Fig. 4. Vynnyky-*Lisivka*, region Lviv. A cluster of burnt clay in trench 3 from the year 2016 (photo: M. Rybicka).

context of specific zones distinguished in the surroundings of the cluster of construction clay [Havinskyj, Rybicka 2021].

All things considered, it seems that in the excavated part of the Vynnyky-*Lisivka* settlement there were uncovered remains of two structures. The bigger one, build using daub, was most likely oriented along the N-S axis (fig. 5). Due to the state of preservation of the feature, it is hard to estimate its original dimensions. Based on the layout of the construction clay, we could deduce that southern and northern walls of the construction collapsed to the western direction. It is the remains of those walls that were documented during the fieldworks in a form of clusters of burnt daub. Judging from analogous features, we could interpret the structure as remains of a dwelling. For example, a cluster of construction clay of very similar layout was identified during an excavation of the central structure of the settlement in Annapol, site 1, belonging to the eastern group of the FBC (fig. 6) [Papiernik, Rybicka 2002, 28, fig. 13-14; Rybicka 2004, 175]. The manner of utilizing the area surrounding the latter dwelling was not purely economic. It seems that the space may have been used for some additional social functions, most likely of a ritual nature [Rybicka 2004, 196-198]. The period of FBC occupation of Annapol, site 1, was dated between 3500-3300 BC [Rybicka 2004; 2017]. The case of Vynnyky-*Lisivka*, there are no features in the surrounding of the clay house suggesting its non-economic purpose.

Detailed analysis of distribution of artifacts near the house at the Vynnyky-*Lisivka* site did not result in identifying zones that could have been used only for one specific activity. The area with most of the waste was located north, east, and south of the construction. What is more, this part of the surroundings of the dwelling was sporadically utilized for economic purposes. We could deduce that such activities may have taken place in this zone based on discovered flint artefacts (fig. 7), as well as potsherds (fig. 8). Similarly, spindle whorls were unearthed in few places around the structure (fig. 8), which suggests that probably there were no separate spaces where they would

be used. The area to the west of the dwelling likely was not so intensively utilized (fig. 4; 6-7). It should be noted that no recessed objects sunken features of an economic function were unearthed near the building. Thus, based on the manner of performing various economic activities in the area around the house, we should interpret the space as a courtyard [comp. Grygiel 1986, 277; Pelisiak 1985; 2003; Rybicka 2004].

According to Andrzej Pelisiak [Pelisiak 2003, 120-121], a prehistoric a house and its yard, with surrounding pits and artefacts, meets the definition of a farm. The scholar described many possible purposes of a yard, including those linked with preparing food, as well as manufacturing and repairing tools. It seems that the area around the analysed dwelling from Vynnyky-*Lisivka* could be treated as such.

The second building discovered at the site, whose construction was based on posts, was oriented along the E-W axis and much smaller than the dwelling described above. It is hard to determine the specific function of the structure; although we could suspect that it could have served some economic purposes. Functionally, the building may have been a part of the yard, integrally linked to the house. We need to keep in mind, however, that at the present state of research we cannot precisely estimate the size of an area of immediate surroundings of the dwelling.

Discussion

As noted by Aleksander Koško [Koško 1981, 149], “the wide application of clay in construction

Fig. 5. Vynnyky-*Lisivka*, region Lviv. Distribution of daub and postholes. 2016-2019 excavation.

to finishing earthen floors and erecting walls (built in a wattle and daub method) represent a complete *novum* in cultural tradition of the Lowland societies. The new technique is strongly correlated with the presence of the *Mątywy cultural component*?. Accord-

ing to the researcher, construction details of one of Late Neolithic dwellings discovered in Kuyavia closely resembled those of a TC house [Koško 1981, 149].

Various remarks on the theories of Aleksander Koško [Koško 1981; 1988] were included in the

Fig. 6. Annapol, Mazowieckie province, central Poland. Distribution of daub within the concentration designated as house 3. A: layer I (40-50 cm below the ground surface); B: Distribution of settlement features in the region of house 3. 1- postholes; 2 – pits; 3 – layer of daub; 4 – layer of clay [5 – layer of clay with an admixture of an undetermined grey substance 6 – quernstone [after Papiernik, Rybicka 2002, fig. 14].

publication of FBC dwellings from Annapol, site 1, Mazovian province [Papiernik, Rybicka 2002], since the more recent research proves that the custom of using daub in construction of houses on the Polish Lowlands was not always associated with the so-called “Mątwy group” of the FBC [Rybicka 2004]. What is more, it seems that Lowland FBC communities knew the technique of plastering walls of dwellings much earlier than previously thought, that is in the initial Sarnowo phase [comp. Wiklak

1986, 172; Rybicka 2004, 201]. The presence of the know-how was documented in various regions and chronological stages of the eastern group [Wawrzykowska 1981, 110; Koško, Szymt 2015; Tetzlaff 1981, 171-172; Diachenko et al. 2018; Pelisiak 1985; 2003; Rzepecki 2014; Grygiel 2016], as well as in the south-eastern group of the FBC [Gumiński 1989, 23-25; Pipes et al. 2014]. Consequently, at the present stage of research, the hypothesis of Aleksander Koško [Koško 1981; 1988] claiming that Lowland societies of the Mątwy group of the FBC adapted the technique of using clay in house building from Eastern European communities seems quite debatable.

To explain whether the emergence of FBC dwellings whose walls and floors were covered by a thick layer of clay plaster could have been caused by influences of the TC, first we should analyse building techniques in the border zone of the two cultures.

Clusters of burnt daub were identified during archaeological research at few FBC settlements in the Bug River basin, such as Gródek Nadbużny [Kowalczyk 1958; Poklewski 1958; Gumiński 1989], Zimno [Pelechishin 2004], and Lezhnitsa [Rybicka et al. 2019]. The area of the features varied from 8 m² [Lezhnitsa, Rybicka et al. 2019] to 20 m² [Gumiński 1989, 22-24]. A relatively small cluster discovered in Lezhnitsa consisted of fragments less than 5 cm in diameter, sometimes with imprints of wattle. The thickness of the feature measured from 10 to 23 cm. During

the excavation of the layer, researchers discovered a large number of artefacts [Rybicka et al. 2019, 14-15]. The state of preservation of the burnt daub unearthed in Gródek Nadbużny differed of those in the cluster from Lezhnitsa [Gumiński 1989, 22-24]. Witold Gumiński noted that such features, the area of whose could reach 20 m², consisted of “lumps of clay with loess, dried or burnt to varying degrees, often mixed with chaff or chopped straw. Diameters of larger fragments rarely exceeded 30 cm, and irregular shaped pieces prevailed over fragments of rectangular corners and even ‘tiles’ 2-4 cm thick” [Gumiński 1989, 22]. On fragments of daub from Gródek Nadbużny were preserved imprints of posts, twigs, and wattle. Detailed analysis of the debris revealed no fragments

Fig. 7. Vynnyky-Lisivka, region Lviv. Distribution of flint artifacts in the trench from the years 2016-2019. Level 20-60 cm.

of earthen floors or collapsed ceilings. Thus, the clusters of daub could represent remains of walls of constructions built without foundations, the outer and inner side of which were covered with clay. According to W. Gumiński [Gumiński 1989], the structures collapsed inwards. Similarly, to the feature from Lezhnitsa, the layers of construction

clay found in Gródek Nadbużny yielded a large number of archaeological finds.

Witold Gumiński [Gumiński 1989, 25] believed that the clusters of daub excavated in Gródek Nadbużny, dubbed 'ploshchadkas', may have been inspired by the architecture of Eastern European cultural circles. The scholar noted that similar fea-

Fig. 9. Vynnyky-*Lisivka*, region Lviv. Distribution of pottery (2) and spindles (1) in the trench from the years 2016-2019. Level 40-60 cm.

tures were unearthed at FBC settlements in Lezhnitsa [Rybicka et al. 2019] and Zimno [Peleshchishin 2004]. Both in Gródek Nadbużny and Zimno [Peleshchishin 2004], archaeologists discovered many examples of imported vessels representing the CII phase of the TC [Gumiński 1989, 53-54, fig. 40; Zawisłak 2013; Rybicka 2017], as well as finds from Volhynian flint [Balcer 1983; Diachenko, Rybicka 2019]. In the opinion of Bogdan

Balcer [Balcer 1983], the FBC settlement in Gródek Nadbużny played a crucial role in trading artefacts made from this raw material. Imports of TC pottery were also identified in the collection from Lezhnitsa [Rybicka et al. 2019, 40-42].

During the existence of the FBC settlements in Western Volhynia described above, the western frontier of TC oecumene of the early CII phase was reaching the Ikva River [Rybicka 2017; Verte-

letsykyi 2020]. Thus, the area between the latter watercourse and the middle Horyn River could be treated as the borderland of the FBC and TC [Rybicka 2017]. Numerous FBC imports found at TC settlements [Pasterkiewicz et al. 2013], as well as cases of syncretism such as those observed in Novomalin-Podobanka [Diachenko et al. 2016; Rybicka 2017], show the intensity of cultural contacts between communities representing the FBC and TC in Western Volhynia. Yet, there is still room for discussion regarding character of TC dwellings from the region. According to Aleksandr Diachenko [Diachenko 2016], a cluster of burnt daub excavated in Nowomalin-Podobanka should be interpreted as remains of a 'ploshchadka', making it the first well-documented feature of this kind from Western Volhynia. This theory was recently challenged by Dmytro Verteletskyi [Verteletskyi 2020], who pointed out that the layout of the feature is consistent with the characteristics of furnaces [comp. Diachenko, Sobkowiak-Tabaka 2020, 149]. For that reason, it seems that we still do not have enough data to determine if FBC dwellings from Western Volhynia showed similarities to TC houses from the region.

Remains of a FBC dwelling discovered in Vynnyky-*Lisivka* differ significantly from remains of houses identified in Gródek Nadbużny [Gumiński 1989]. Among the most essential disparities, we

should name lack of sunken features (such as furnaces), size of clusters of construction clay, frequency of archaeological finds, as well as manner of collapsing walls. The layout of daub fragments in the feature from Vynnyky-*Lisivka* resembles dwellings of the eastern group of the FBC on the Polish Lowlands [Pelisiak 1985; 2002; 2003; Papiernik, Rybicka 2002; Rybicka 2004]. We should keep in mind, however, that remains of houses found in Vynnyky-*Lisivka*, Gródek Nadbużny [Gumiński 1989], and Lezhnitsa [Rybicka et al. 2019] clearly diverge from the classical TC dwellings [Markevich 1981], both in terms of construction techniques as well as internal layout. On the other hand, clusters of burnt daub interpreted as a debris of FBC houses with no foundations show some resemblances to remains of light TC constructions. Examples of such structures are known from sites Kurgany-Dubova [Diachenko 2016] or Vynnyky-*Zhupan* [Diachenko et al. 2019], dated to the late 4th Millennium BC [Rybicka et al. 2019, Table 4]. As it was already mentioned, very similar buildings are characteristic for the eastern group of the FBC [Pelisiak 2003; Rybicka 2004]. At the present state of research, there is still not enough information to assess if the observed parallels between dwellings of the FBC and those of younger stages of the TC could be linked to similar settlement systems and economy, specifically with more mobile way of life.

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